

ECOFEMINIST CRITICISM OF ANIMAL RIGHTS ETHICS

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7916602

Larissa Lunkes de Souza

Master's student in philosophy at PPGFil at PUCRS, graduated with a laureate in philosophy at the same institution. Research with an emphasis on contemporaneity, ecofeminism, oppression, structure, domination. Email: larissa.souza.003@acad.pucrs.br.

SUMMARY

The ethical-philosophical theoretical field of animal rights is consolidated especially in two aspects: welfare, structured in utilitarian ethics, defending the moral criterion of sentience, ability to feel pain and pleasure, and with this criterion it seeks to work hypotheses for animal welfare. animal being, whose main theorist of this aspect is the philosopher Peter Singer. Abolitionism, on the other hand, uses the reformulation of deontological ethics developed by the thinker Tom Regan, proposing a shift from the moral framework of “rationality” to “being-subject-of-a-life”. Despite following different theoretical lines, the ecofeminists, especially Marti Kheel, confirm that the arguments in favor of animal rights seek to establish the overvaluation of the rational basis, impartiality and universality to the detriment of any emotional sphere, such as the values of empathy and care, which in turn are associated with the feminine. In this way, both theoretical lines end up using antro/andro-centric lenses and assumptions that fundamentally neglect the interests/rights of both women and animals. Thus, the central problem of the work is to identify why ecofeminists are dissatisfied with the animalist field of welfarism and abolitionism. Therefore, the objective of this work is to briefly present the traditional ethics of animal rights and their respective criticisms, showing that ecofeminists develop another possibility for the animalist field: the ethics of care.

Keywords: Ethic; Utilitarianism; Deontology; Abolitionism; Feminism.

INTRODUCTION

Since the beginning of philosophy, animalist issues were present, with their different judgments, going to the Pythagorean conception of metempsychosis in which animals share a common soul with human animals, to modernity, with Descartes, and the mechanistic notion of animal bodies. This means that, the thought about what non-human animals are, or what are our responsibilities towards them, in a certain way, have always been present at the edges ¹of

¹ as a secondary and even irrelevant issue.

Western philosophy. Whether it was to claim that they could be used as things or to treat them with compassion.

In contemporary times, these issues leave the edges to host the core of ethical-philosophical reflection. This mobility receives influences from its historical moment, specifically from the 60's/70's of the 20th century, in which there is an expansion of social movements, such as, for example: the feminist, black, environmentalist, and hippie movements. The counterculture context allows some philosophers to reflect on animalist issues and become indignant when faced with the violent conditions in which animals are subjected.

Thus, the concern of the first philosophers within the field of animalist research was to demoralize the torturous conditions that we submit animals and to present justifications for why these were morally reprehensible actions. You see, there is an explicit notion that the way we treat animals is wrong whereas there is a right way we should treat them. In other words, an indignation arises that is tried to be proved as legitimate within the already consolidated perspectives of philosophical ethics.

Ethics of Animal Rights: Welfarism and Abolitionism

The first philosopher to carry out this movement is Australian Peter Singer, current professor at Princeton University, author of famous books, especially *Animal Liberation* (1975). This becomes his most influential work, as it represents the beginning of an animal ethics not only concerned with companion animals (dogs and cats), but all sentient ones, meaning: “(...) *the capacity to suffer and/ or experiencing pleasure*” (SINGER, 2008, p.10).

The philosopher who most influenced Singer was Jeremy Bentham (1748-1832), considered to have formulated ²the ethical doctrine of utilitarianism. The jurist made it clear that the animalist question should be reviewed:

Perhaps the day will come when the rest of the animal creation will acquire the rights which they could never have been denied but by the hand of tyranny. The French have already discovered that the darkness of the skin is no reason why a human being should be irremediably abandoned to the whims of a torturer. It is possible that one day it will be recognized that the number of legs, the villi of the skin or the termination of the sacral bone are equally insufficient reasons for abandoning a sentient being to the same fate. What else should draw the impassable line? The faculty of reason, or perhaps the capacity for language? But an adult horse or dog is incomparably more rational and communicative than a day-old, week-old, or even month-old baby. Supposing, however, that things were not so, what importance would

²Hume gave the first insights into a utilitarian morality, Bentham formulates it and Mill reformulates it.

that fact have? The question is not “Are they able to reason?” nor “Are they able to speak?” but rather “Are they able to suffer?” (BENTHAM apud SINGER, 2009, p. 9).

The reason that allows Bentham to perceive the immorality of the way we treat animals is precisely because of the moral principle of utility that preaches the supremacy of happiness. Thus, what matters is the ability to experience pleasure, happiness, pain and unhappiness, rather than establishing a line in which beings x and y can be subjected to pain without “any justification”³.

Therefore, the most radical criterion of utilitarianism opens a gap for morally considering other beings besides humans. Because of this, James Rachels (2006, p.99) understands that for Bentham and his follower John Stuart Mill, tormenting a human would be wrong because he suffers, and it would be similarly wrong to cause pain to non-human animals because they suffer, being a conclusive and resulting reasoning. In view of this, it can be concluded that Bentham does not specifically theorize about the animal question, but leaves the path that utility must consider the suffering involved in them.

Taking advantage of the insights left by Bentham, Peter Singer develops *the principle of equal consideration of interests* with the following premises: morality is formulated from interests, defined by our capacities; equality is a prescription of how we should treat the other, that is, when we say that all human beings are equal, it does not mean that they are in fact, but that we should treat them as if they were, without overvaluing one and deteriorating the other (2009 , p. 06). Thus, the principle ensures that similar interests are considered equally, since the novelty is the inclusion of the “who” in the appeal for equality.

The need to develop this principle is because, according to Singer (2009, p. 06), the interests of various human and non-human entities were neglected due to prejudice, such as, for example, sexism, racism and speciesism⁴. Through these prejudices, an arbitrary line of morality is established, in which these beings are excluded from the sphere only by their gender, skin color or species.

However, animals were historically considered as things, so the question is: What distinguishes animals from objects? What makes them interested and things like rocks, trees and cell phones not? Singer responds as follows:

³The quotation marks are because there are anthropocentric and speciesist justifications. That is, justifications that completely ignore them as entities of moral considerations.

⁴ term coined by Richard D. Ryder to name a moral claim solely based on species, but becoming popular through Singer's work.

The capacity to suffer and to experience pleasure is a prerequisite for having any interest, a condition which must be satisfied before we can speak of interest in an understandable way [...] The capacity to suffer and to experience pleasure, however, not only is it necessary, but also sufficient for us to ensure that a being has interests - at least, the interest of not suffering (2009, p. 09).

In this way, it can be concluded that Singer is the first philosopher to place non-human animals as entities of moral value through their capacity for sentience. According to Sônia Felipe, the author states: *“All beings capable of feeling pain, discomfort and displeasure for prolonged periods, to the point that such experiences become suffering, have intrinsic value”* (2006, p.130).

In contrast, it is necessary to point out that, when exchanging moral status, it is intended that animals will only have interests related to sentience, that is, only not suffering and being able to enjoy their existence according to their instincts and needs. This means that the preached animal liberation is only referring to mistreatment and the suffering involved and not against their use.

In other words, using animals while respecting their interests caused by sentience is justified by: (1) if sentience is their only capability, then it is all to consider; (2) humans, because they have more capabilities, will have more interests and, thus, respecting what sentience implies, will only increase happiness and pleasure.

Due to the reasons presented, the animalist ethics proposed by Peter Singer, will come to be placed as an ethics of well-being in which he would be the intellectual leader of the movement. However, some critics, such as the abolitionist Gary Francione, rectify this analysis: *“[...] Singer claims much more for non-human animals than an improvement in their living conditions or humane treatment, but an autonomous moral status, founded on on equal terms with regard to their basic interests”* (GRANT, 2011, p.278).

Michael Sandel highlights one of Kant's criticisms of Bentham's ethics: *“By basing rights on a calculation about what will produce the greatest happiness, he argues, utilitarianism leaves these rights vulnerable ”* (2015, p.138). This criticism of utilitarianism continues for theories of animal welfare, as this way of defending the interests of animals keeps the interests of animals fragile and, because of this, they continue to be objectified - mere means. Susin and Zampiere expounds this critique of abolitionists as follows:

(...) our speciesist practice that exploits, demeans, causes suffering and death, both in the meat and fur industry and in research, games, entertainment and, above all, food, needs simply to, and not just become more “humane”. There can be no “humanitarian torture”. It's all or nothing (2015, p.137).

The expression above: “all or nothing”, presents the spirit of the intellectual/social movement that will succeed well-being within the field of animalist ethics. Its name is derived from the verb to abolish, and its objective is to end all forms of animal exploitation. In this sense, exploitation refers to the way in which abolitionists understand that the human/animal relationship is established.

The pioneering spirit of this perspective appears with the work *Vazias Jaulas* (2003), by the philosopher Tom Regan. The author is philosophically influenced by Kantian perspectives and in his practical life he becomes an activist for human rights, which, as Sandel shows, has Kantian bases in its constitution (2015, p.137). Thus, their most imminent difference to Singer is the result of the influences they use to reflect the animal issue: Regan is concerned with moral/inalienable rights while Singer is concerned with consequences and the satisfaction of interests.

Regan initially devoted himself to studies on human rights and concluded that all human beings had inherent moral rights, such as physical integrity, liberty and life. For the author, there are other rights that are evaluative, such as the consequences, but they could never transgress the inalienable rights, as they are primordial and set by themselves.

In view of this, for him, the problem of whether we have these rights was resolved, we had the rights we do – to our freedom, bodily integrity and life – what caused him the “itch of thought” was why. Thus, the author shows the main arguments used to justify why we have moral rights: “Human beings are human; human beings are people; human beings are self-aware; human beings use speech; human beings live in a moral community; human beings have souls; God gave us these rights.” (REGAN, 2006, p.53).

According to the author, the problem is that these reasons do not satisfactorily justify why we have the rights we have, because they are either true and irrelevant, or relevant and false, or based on religious dogmas⁵. When looking for what would be true and relevant, what would in fact justify our existence so that we have inherent value, he comes to the conclusion that it is our ability to be aware in the world and the things that happen to us that matter to us. Thus, he develops the subject-of-a-life concept, meaning:

As subjects-of-a-life, we are all equal because what happens to us (with our bodies, our freedom or our lives) is important to us (...) As subjects-of-a-life, there is no superior nor inferior, there is no better or worse. As subjects-of-a-life, we are all morally identical (REGAN, 2006, p.62) .

⁵Examples: human beings have rights because they are human is true, but irrelevant as it is a tautology; human beings have rights because they are persons, is relevant, but false, as not everyone can be considered a person.

Note that Regan uses the category of equality just like Singer, but not because of the consequences felt, but rather considering the moral status of beings. Thus, those who are subjects-of-a-life have a relationship of equality with other beings in terms of moral status and, *prima facie*, the importance of their moral rights.

Therefore, from the deontological perspective, moral rights arise by themselves, they cannot be withdrawn or given away, they can be neglected or respected. However, the subject will always be a being who has inalienable rights, because of this Regan says: “ As subjects-of-a-life, we are equal because what happens to us is important to us, whether others care about it, whether no” (REGAN, 2006, p.62).

respect is carried out : "treating these individuals without exception as ends in themselves, and not just as instruments for the best consequences/interests of others" (2014, P.178). This principle, obviously, results in the principle of harm, meaning the duty, especially of moral agents, not to harm such beings – whether they are moral agents or patients ⁶.

Until now, being a subject-of-a-life justified only human rights, but it becomes extremely relevant for animalist reflection: “among the billions of non-human animals, are there animals aware of the world and what happens to them? (...) If there are animals that meet this requirement, they are subjects-of-a-life”.

Regan notes six reasons why animals are subjects-of-a-life, namely: common sense, common language, common behavior, common bodies, common systems, and common origins. These arguments are interconnected , but the basic one is the theory of evolution, as the author describes: “Not only the fact that we exist, but what we are , cannot be understood separately from other forms of life” (REGAN, 2006, p. 60).

Darwin demonstrates that humans have common ancestors with other species of animals, leading to similarities in anatomical, systemic, and mental capabilities. When the scientist states that: “(...) the difference in mind between man and the higher animals, however great they may be, is certainly one of degree and not of type” (1981, p.105, free translation) ⁷, he is corroborating the thesis that animals are potentially rational ⁸, an argument that would elevate animals to the status of moral patients.

⁶Moral agents would be those who can take responsibility for their actions within a moral community and patients are those who cannot and should be protected in this community.

⁷ In the original: Nevertheless the difference in mind between man and the higher animals, great as it is, is certainly one of degree and not of kind.

⁸In the Kantian deontological argument, moral patients such as children, women and people with neurodivergent disorders would be potentially rational and, therefore, should be protected in a moral community.

So, in an extremely simplistic way, non-human animals would be subjects-of-a-life because: 1) they are similar to humans in ancestry, anatomy, system and mental capacity; 2) the sentience of animals expands to feel pain and pleasure, but they allow them to feel fear, disgust, anguish and love; 3) thus, we can understand their behavior and what they communicate, as they work in a similar way to ours; 4) finally: “To question animal consciousness is to question the veracity of common sense” (REGAN, 1983, p.2, free translation) ⁹.

The strategy addressed by the author is to bring humans closer to animals, in order to justify why animals are subjects-of-a-life. However, the animal kingdom encompasses profoundly different beings. So: Who are the animals that have moral rights? They are, for the author, especially mammals, but can extend to birds, fish and vertebrates.

The author states that more animals could be subjects-of-a-life, but he delimits it so as not to lose the force of the argument. Also, we emphasize that Regan seeks to justify as *subjects-of-a-life* those animals that are most used as things in the production of things for humans: food industries, laboratory tests, clothing manufacturing and entertainment ¹⁰.

Animalist critique of animal rights

Welfare believes that the improvement of the conditions to which animals are submitted takes place in changes that take into account their biological, individual and social needs, such as, for example, being raised in fields, larger and cleaner cages, development of stunning techniques for the slaughter... In their opposition, the abolitionists believe that these measures are a failed attempt, for: “*Simply to reform injustice is to prolong injustice*” (NACONECY, 2014, p.180) , so the issue is to radicalize by eliminating any use and ways in which humans treat animals as things. So they propose different things, however:

In general terms, both philosophers share the conviction that (i) many species of animals have moral status, (ii) that the differences between humans and animals are not such as to justify the way in which we treat them, and (iii) that this status demands broad reforms in our customs (2014, p.179).

This is because both theorists have the same motivational assumptions based on the historical context of the counterculture that resulted in moral indignation. Thus, even if they are following different lines, their objective from the beginning was the same: to ethically justify that the way in which we treat animals is a moral absurdity. Therefore, it can be concluded that

⁹In the original: question animal awareness is to question the veracity of common sense itself.

¹⁰It is something noticeable in the work Jaulas Vazias, in all the author's examples he deals with these types of animals and by his indignation in the way in which we treat them.

philosophical lines, utilitarianism or deontology, served as a rational pretext to justify a belief already considered true.

Thus, the animalist philosophy becomes a kind of applied ethics and incapable of going to the roots and formulating a system of its own. When framing animalist concerns in already established ethics, this always has a central weakness, that of being just an interpretation applied to animals. The biggest problem with this is that the ethics used to interpret it were developed through an anthro/andro-centric lens, so at the root of these ethics there is a neglect of the interests/rights of animals and women.

Naconezy also points out that: “(...) in practice, Singer's utilitarianism and Regan's position of rights are concerned with the same types of animals” (2014, p.179), these being mainly the ones that esare being domesticated and used in favor of human wills. Thus, its contextual bases used are industries, factories, laboratories and breeding grounds.

In this way, the proposals of both are precarious to deal with wild animals, which, as Marti Kheel mentions: “For wild animals, the greatest act of care can be to leave them alone” (KHEEL, 2019, 39). In order to be able to leave these animals alone, it is essential to protect the forests, however, in both authors, nature has no interests or rights. In Singer's criterion, nature such as plants are not sentient and, therefore, there would be no interest em in considering them. In Regan, all the criteria used to assume rights for animals could hardly be extended to nature.

Both utilitarianism and deontology preach impartiality, universality, and especially the overvaluation of rigorous logic in argumentation. By following these lines, the authors incorporate these values and seek to convince that animals have interests/rights and that, because of this, we should care and treat them with respect. Marti Kheel criticizes such authors on this point:

Both theorists proudly proclaimed that nowhere in their books will one find any reference to emotion or claims that could not be supported by rigorous logic; it is logic alone that can compel right conduct. And yet it was the feelings of empathy and care that drew me to the animal movement in the first place. I felt something was missing (KHEEL, 2019, 30).

The author questions the contempt that traditional ethics have in relation to the emotional spheres, because in addition to her own example, we can mention the authors themselves being criticized. What unites Singer's and Regan's approaches is their own - emotional - indignation that there are no justifications for treating animals as humans have been treated. Thus, for her and ecofeminism, the animalist issue must focus on empathy and care.

In this direction, the author writes: “(...) an ethics of holistic care also implies supporting the potential for empathy that exists within each of us” (KHEEL, 2019, 38). Then, he points to the arts as a strategic means to unlock this empathic capacity and states that films, such as: *Babe, the clumsy little pig*, are more successful in making people act in relation to animals than arguments on a rational basis (KHEEL, 2019, 38).

Because arguments do not motivate action, the author realizes that ecofeminist perspectives have a more interesting place to incorporate animalist issues. Then:

Most ecofeminists were not trying to develop foundational arguments for why people should care for nature (and animals), but rather were examining the worldviews that explained why empathy and care for nature was lacking in the first place (KHEEL, 2019, p.32).

Through the identification of the motivations and reasons why there was no empathy and care for the animals, a more objective and efficient strategy formation is possible to make people care and be indignant with the situation in which the animals find themselves. I conclude with Kheel's famous phrase: “*Thus, why people should take care of animals may be less important than why they do not*” (2019, p.37).

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The related work is situated within animalist and gender studies, however within traditional animalism, interpretations that include gender analyzes are neglected and sidelined. Sometimes intentionally, considering that it is not just about animalism or, on the other hand, they are not known.

Thus, our objective was to briefly present the main areas of research within philosophical animalism, highlighting their differences, but especially, showing that they have a range of common epistemological values. And, moreover, they started from a common belief that there are not enough rational motivations for us to treat non-human animals the way we treat them.

Finally, when understanding the limitations of these perspectives, it is possible to perceive that ecofeminists not only bring gender issues to animalism because gender is a demand of them, but that yes, it makes it possible to understand horizons – dare I say it – more significant than rationality. Furthermore, ecofeminist epistemologies allow us to delve into the influences of emotion, care and empathy, as well as, through this, teach us to understand and relate to non-human animals in a different and more respectful way.

REFERENCES

- DARWIN, C. *The Descent of Man, and selection in relation to sex*. New Jersey: Princeton University Press, 1981.
- FELIPE, Inherent Value and Vulnerability: Non-speciesist Ethical Criteria from Tom Regan's Perspective. In: *ethic@*, Florianópolis, vol. 5, n.3, 2006. Available at: < <https://periodicos.ufsc.br/index.php/ethic/article/view/24877> >.
- GRANT, Caroline. ABOLITIONISM AND ANIMAL RIGHT – DECONSTRUCTING PARADIGMS: an approach from the perspective of movements in favor of animal rights and the ethics of care. In: *Brazilian Journal of Animal Law*, Bahia, v. 6, n.8, 2011. Available at: < <https://periodicos.ufba.br/index.php/RBDA/article/view/11063> > .
- KHEEL, Marti. The contribution of ecofeminism to animal ethics. In: ROSENDO, Daniela et al. *Ecofeminisms : theoretical foundations and intersectional praxis*. Rio de Janeiro: Botafogo, Ape'Ku, 2019.
- NACONECY, Carlos. *ETHICS & ANIMALS : a guide to philosophical argumentation*. Porto Alegre: ediPUCRS, 2014.
- RACHELS, James. *The Elements of Moral Philosophy*. São Paulo- Tamboré: Manole, 2006.
- REGAN, Tom. *Empty cages : facing the challenges of animal rights*. Porto Alegre: Lugano, 2006.
- REGAN, T. *The Case for Animals Right*. Berkeley: University of California Press, 1983.
- SANDEL, Michael. *Justice : what it is to do the right thing*. Rio de Janeiro: Brazilian Civilization, 2015.
- SINGER, Peter. *Animal Liberation*. Porto Alegre, Sao Paulo: Lugano, Evolução Editora, 2008.
- SUSIN, Luiz; ZAMPIERI, Gilmar. *The Lives of Others : Ethics and Animal Liberation Theology*. Sao Paulo, Paulinas, 2015.